

THE IMPORTANCE OF LANGUAGE TEACHING USING INTERESTING METHODOLOGIES

Qarshiyeva Mushtariy Tolibovna
Termez State University 1st year student
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6413449>

Annotation. This article discusses the different types of methods used in teaching a foreign language to schoolchildren and how to arouse their interest in the language through their use.

Key words: method, foreign language, communication skills, dialogical speech, motivation.

Method (Greek "metodos" - a way of knowing or research, theory, doctrine) - a method of practical and theoretical acquisition, mastering, study, guidelines for learning, a set of methods, the creation and substantiation of philosophical knowledge.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European languages (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Persian, Turkish, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our country. These languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions, and to date, the lessons are taught by specialists using certain types of methods in different processes. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural state and the foreign language in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language is mainly divided into communication only during English lessons at the request of the teacher and the subject. Learning a foreign language in three languages requires specific teaching methods and technologies to engage students in that language.

The term method is used to mean "set of teaching methods" and "direction of education". The subject of the methodology is the process and methods of teaching through the subject of foreign languages, the science of teaching foreign languages, the activities of teachers and students and the relationship between them. Research shows that learning a second language boosts problem solving, critical thinking and listening skills, in addition to improving memory, concentration and the ability to multitask. Children proficient in other languages also show signs of enhanced creativity and mental flexibility.¹

¹Academic research in educational sciences. Modern methods in foreign language teaching methodology. Z.Sanakulov.524-525pages.

Present day English is the simplest adaptation of a very old language and yet it is still difficult to teach this language affectively especially to those who speak English as a second or even third language. The traditional “chalk and talk” method of teaching that’s persisted for hundreds of years is now acquiring inferior results when compared with the more modern and revolutionary teaching methods that are available for use in schools today this method is a technique that creates a conversation , mutual opinions and comments among learners through writing.

Chalk Talk is a silent conversation in writing that allows students to have an equal opportunity to participate. It is a versatile protocol that can be used for many purposes. Students and teachers love it.

A *chalk talk* is a monologue presentation done while the speaker draws. It is usually done with chalk, hard crayon, or pastel, or with dry-erase markers on a whiteboard. Through using "chalk talk" in the 3 previous items , the teacher can do a self -reflection when he sees the "chalk talk" done by learners and he can compare it with the learning objectives of the lesson.

A Chalk Talk is a silent activity that provides all students the opportunity to reflect on what they know, and then share their thinking and wonderings while connecting to the thoughts of their classmates.²

Dialogical speech – in this way students have a talk each other by creative approach. Modern Methodology of teaching English puts speaking in dialogues in the first place for developing speaking skills. These skills can be trained with various teaching aids, including texts of fiction. More than that, all the vocabularies learned by heart is remembered much better when a pupil starts to use them in a speech. In dialogues pupils train in fluency, quick reaction and of course grammatical structures and correctness. The use of the conversational method to develop fluent speech in children gives good results. Through short question and answer, children's vocabulary expands and fluent speech develops. Grammar teaching is an essential aspect of education and without proper grammar, writing, reading, and speaking all lose meaning and value. So because of the impact of this method children improve their correctness in speech step by step.

1. *Understanding by reading.* Pupils read short stories on their books themselves and tells the main meaning of the story. Reading is very helpful to increase the horizon of thinking. Reading texts, fairy tales, poems and other literary works written by famous Uzbek and English writers is very

² <http://www.bchmsg.yolasite.com/chalk-talk.php>

important in language learning moreover by that you can come across unfamiliar words that build vocabulary of new strategical words. For example: you should observe a material for an overview of content, read the material and take notes, remember what you have read and review it.

2. *Another great point is Motivation.* It is widely agreed that motivation has great influence on pupils capacity to learn. The good news for teachers is that there are many things we can do in the classroom to increase the level of motivation. Motivation is an important factor in learning a foreign language which is influenced by different variables. Motivation sometimes overlooked by some EFL teachers in urging their learners to learn more. We as EFL teachers should promote motivation. Teachers should help their learners to find motivation in the areas where they don't expect it and also to research for their own motivational processes so they can take advantage of it.³ motivation answers the question of why a person is learning a language. The motivation here refers to the goal of learning a language. Harmer (1991) used the word "goal" to classify the motivation in language learning into two different types which include: (a) Short-term goal: It means that students wish to succeed in doing something in the near future. For example, students who want to pass their examination or get a good grade/high scores. (b) Long-term goal: It refers to a wish that students want to get a better job in the future and be able to communicate with people who use the language (the target language) that they learn.⁴

3. *Playing brainstorm games, doing crosswords, finding the correct words throw other verbs.* In addition to developing the students intellect, playing a variety of games relieves the pupils' fatigue and clears the brain. Circle games are very useful activities that involve the whole class, sitting in a circle. Games help students to make and sustain the effort of learning. They provide language practice in the various skills – speaking, writing, listening and reading. They encourage pupils to interact and communicate. They create a meaningful context for language use. The main reason why games are considered effective learning aids is that "they spur motivation and students get very absorbed in the competitive aspects of the games; moreover, they try harder at games than in other courses"

4 *Beneficial ways of using videos in the lesson.* Videos, presentations always help pupils to understand the theme easily and fast without any difficulties.

³International Journal of Research in English Education journal. The impact of motivation on English language learning. M. Alizadeh. 2016.18.11. 14-page.

⁴European Journal of Educational, EJES Motivation in Learning English Language March 2019

They can bring the outside world to learners introducing different cultures, new places and ideas. They provide a great way to integrate new content and language learning at the same time – giving students the opportunity to learn about a whole range of subjects and ideas, at the same time as learning language. Videos also provide context to help understanding. Unlike reading texts and listening activities, video provides strong visual cues. These help learners understand what’s happening – even the language is hard to follow.

In some cases, you can even play videos without sound at first and have the pupils guess what’s happening and said. This helps in a similar way to a reading prediction activity and helps prepare the schoolchildren. What’s more globally, there are many more people who speak English as a second language than there are native speakers. So it’s a good idea to expose your class to a variety of non-nativespeakers in videos.

In conclusion, in order to facilitate the learning of English, teachers should direct students to find similarities and differences in Uzbek and English. Foreign language teaching methods form the student's ability to apply the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in English in everyday life, in a specific field, in everyday life.

USED LITERATURE:

1. Jalolov J. “Chet tilinio’qitishmetodikasi”Toshkent,1996
2. Sanakulov.Z.“Modern methods in foreign language teaching, methodology,2021
3. KappasA.Zh. “New generation- new methods of foreign language teaching.
4. M.Alizadeh.International Journal of Research in English Education journal.The impact of motivation on English language learning. 2016.18.11. 14-page.